

The Philotis Platform: Empowering Low-Resource Languages Processing

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1 Introduction

The project Philotis has developed a web-based platform¹ and a methodology, implemented as a pipeline, for recording, analyzing, and documenting living languages in real-life contexts. The platform incorporates cutting-edge multi-modal technologies (text, image, audio). The tools have been integrated into an advanced digital platform designed for language analysis and documentation, employing machine learning techniques. The creation of resources from scratch is known to be a challenging and time-consuming task due to, inter alia, the lack of documentation, the difficulty in the accessibility of materials, the need for technological support, and the lack of complete and consistent NLP pipelines (Moran and Chiarcos, 2020).

The Philotis platform meets the needs of linguists with little technical knowledge who aim to develop plain and annotated corpora from multi-modal data sources.

Users of the Philotis platform follow the procedure shown in Figure 1 that supports a wide range of settings from non-standardised oral language varieties with no writing system to varieties with the privilege of morphosyntactically annotated treebanks.

Figure 1: Pipeline Workflow.

The platform is tailored to operate in both multi-lingual and low-resource settings through a comprehensive adaptation in five key dimensions. First, its language-agnostic design ensures efficient functionality across linguistic variations. Second, the platform does not require a pre-specified amount or type of data, making it functional to any given settings. Third, its capability to create keyboards facilitates the handling of different writing systems,

a feature of particular significance in the context of endangered languages that often lack a standardized orthography (Lin, 2021). Fourth, the tool is characterized by flexibility, allowing users to generate and choose resources customized to their needs. This adaptability extends to the training of a multi-lingual model, allowing the incorporation of resources from various languages. Thus, knowledge transfer from one language to another becomes feasible, enabling also the acquisition of an initial annotation version. Fifth, the tool aligns with the concept of ‘active annotation’, enabling the incremental use of text fragments and subsequent cycles of training and evaluation. This approach accelerates the generation of a gold corpus, contributing to faster and more efficient annotation processes (Anastasopoulos et al., 2018).

2 Resource development

We will present the pipeline for annotated corpus development from raw resources (recorded speech, text). The users may chose to step into (or exit from) the pipeline at some point other than its start or end, depending on the type of the available resources and on their goals.

We have already noted that Philotis facilitates the creation of new keyboards tailored to the needs of each language (Lin, 2021). The generated file can be used within the Keyman service².

The user starts the procedure of resource development by creating a new corpus project. Each corpus is assigned the following metadata: (i) the name of the corpus, (ii) the language, (iii) the dialect, (iv) a description, (v) the license under which it can be made available to other users (vi) the administrator, and the (vii) the contact person. Next, the ‘Source’ of the corpus is described, uploaded to the platform, and assigned metadata as before. As ‘Source’ is considered a non-empty set of raw txt/doc/pdf/audio files, and images.

In the second step, the user, through the ‘Resources’ component, can select texts from an avail-

¹<https://application.athenarc.gr>

²<https://keyman.com/windows/>

the Docker platform. The Flask framework provides the basis for building RESTful API endpoints that present NLP operations to users, while Docker encapsulates the entire service, including its components and environment, ensuring consistent behavior across different development environments.

The Flask service acts as the interface through which users interact with NLP functions, making requests and receiving responses through well-defined RESTful API endpoints. Leveraging the Stanza library, the Flask service orchestrates the training and updating of NLP models, ensuring that the system remains responsive and accessible even while training models.

The front end has been developed using JavaScript/PHP webpages with Axios⁹ for handling asynchronous HTTP requests. To interact with the back end, the front end uses the RESTful API endpoints provided by the Flask service and integrates NLP functionalities into the user interface. PHP 8.2 has been used to develop the back end; the Laravel 9 framework has been used as an infrastructure. Access to the database is facilitated through MySQL Workbench 8.0¹⁰.

3 Conclusions

In conclusion, the Philotis platform that is presented in this paper is a significant contribution to the field of language documentation and analysis, particularly for low-resource languages. Its user-centric design, comprehensive functionalities, and robust architecture lay a strong foundation for further advancements in linguistic research and preservation efforts. One notable feature is the platform’s provision for downloading raw corpora, golden corpora, models, and predicted annotations. This capability enhances the platform’s utility by enabling users to take advantage of the platform facilities at different stages of the language documentation process. In a nutshell, the Philotis platform can accommodate diverse research needs and methodologies. As this platform continues to evolve, it holds the potential to foster international collaboration among linguists in their endeavors to document and preserve linguistic diversity.

⁹<https://axios-http.com/>

¹⁰<https://dev.mysql.com/downloads/workbench/>

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